

Cover

Pre-commercial procurement of personal health services: Interoperability considerations

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Lähteenmäki, J., Leppänen, J., Sachinopoulou, A., Mathieu, J. P., Alessandrello, R., & Ikävalko, S. (2017). Pre-commercial procurement of personal health services: Interoperability considerations. In M. Macedo, & L. Rodrigues (Eds.), Proceedings of the International Conference on E-Health, EH 2017 - Part of the Multi Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems 2017 (pp. 79-86)</p> <p>Link to Abstract: http://www.iadisportal.org/digital-library/pre-commercial-procurement-of-personal-health-services-%C2%96-interoperability-considerations</p>
<p><i>Abstract</i></p>	<p>Public healthcare providers are increasingly guiding their patients to using personal health services to support self-care. The provider is typically in the role of specifying the required functionalities and purchasing the technologies to be used by the patient. A new pre-commercial procurement (PCP) model has been introduced by the European Union with the objective of increasing use of new innovative technologies and interaction between the procurers and technology suppliers. The model is well fitted for personal health services where there is a high potential for exploiting advanced information and communication technologies (ICT). When applying the PCP model it is important to ensure that the developed prototypes can be integrated to the existing health IT infrastructure. This is particularly important when the developed service needs to exchange information with Electronic Health Record (EHR) or Personal Health Record (PHR) systems. Since the relevant interfaces are still largely missing from existing EHRs and PHRs it is important to provide test interfaces, which enable the developed services to be tested for interoperability during the PCP process. This paper provides background for the interoperability needs of personal health services and describes the test server solution developed in the context of the DECIPHER PCP project. Based on feedback from the supplier companies the test server was an acceptable and useful solution for the development phase as actual PHR interfaces have not yet been implemented by the procurers.</p>

PRE-COMMERCIAL PROCUREMENT OF PERSONAL HEALTH SERVICES – INTEROPERABILITY CONSIDERATIONS

Jaakko Lähtenmäki¹, Juha Leppänen¹, Anna Sachinopoulou¹, Jean Patrick Mathieu²,
Rossana Alessandrello² and Suzan Ikävalko³

¹ VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland - Tietotie 3, FI-02650 Espoo, Finland

² Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (AQUAS) - Carrer de Roc Boronat, 81-95,
08005 Barcelona, Spain

³ Nordic Healthcare Group - Vattuniemenranta 2, FI-00210 Helsinki, Finland

ABSTRACT

Public healthcare providers are increasingly guiding their patients to using personal health services to support self-care. The provider is typically in the role of specifying the required functionalities and purchasing the technologies to be used by the patient. A new pre-commercial procurement (PCP) model has been introduced by the European Union with the objective of increasing use of new innovative technologies and interaction between the procurers and technology suppliers. The model is well fitted for personal health services where there is a high potential for exploiting advanced information and communication technologies (ICT). When applying the PCP model it is important to ensure that the developed prototypes can be integrated to the existing health IT infrastructure. This is particularly important when the developed service needs to exchange information with Electronic Health Record (EHR) or Personal Health Record (PHR) systems. Since the relevant interfaces are still largely missing from existing EHRs and PHRs it is important to provide test interfaces, which enable the developed services to be tested for interoperability during the PCP process. This paper provides background for the interoperability needs of personal health services and describes the test server solution developed in the context of the DECIPHER PCP project. Based on feedback from the supplier companies the test server was an acceptable and useful solution for the development phase as actual PHR interfaces have not yet been implemented by the procurers.

KEYWORDS

Pre-commercial procurement, personal health services, cross-border health, interoperability, interface testing

1. INTRODUCTION

ICT (Information and Communications Technology) based services and applications have shown potential in supporting self-care and health maintenance. Patients with chronic diseases may carry out blood glucose, blood pressure and other measurements at home and share the results with their care providers (Klersy et al., 2009; Orsama et al., 2013). Services and applications may motivate individuals for healthy life styles by tracking physical activity and eating habits. Although a large variety of personal health services is already in the market, there is a high potential for new innovations with impact on personal health and healthcare efficacy.

The exploitation of new technology is currently suboptimal due to the fact, that development of new innovations takes place in companies without either sufficient connection to healthcare provider organizations or knowledge about healthcare domain and its regulatory constraints (e.g. the Medical Device Directive, 93/42/EEC). This often leads to services not matching with the needs of the procurer organizations and end-users. Pre-commercial procurement (PCP) has the potential of combining the R&D work of innovative companies with public procurers' need for new services (Hommen & Rolfstam, 2009). The European Commission has invested in several projects with the objective of developing and demonstrating

viable PCP practices in a variety of industry sectors, including robotics, traffic, boarder security, firemen security and education¹.

This paper addresses the application of PCP to personal health service development in a setting where three procurers from different countries are involved. In such case the interoperability challenges are particularly high, as the developed services and applications should be connectable with existing distributed and fragmented national system infrastructures. Moreover, the related data contents are highly confidential, sensitive and heterogeneous, including structured and unstructured data. At the same time, the services are provided by a diverse group of companies. The paper addresses the PCP process and focuses on the related interoperability challenges, which are especially high in a cross-border setting. We will describe the test server approach set up in the DECIPHER project for ensuring a minimum level of interoperability. DECIPHER is among the first PCP projects initiated in the 7th Framework Programme of the EU.

2. PRE-COMMERCIAL PROCUREMENT

Public healthcare providers have an important role in recruiting patients to self-management programs, monitoring their progress and providing feedback. In many countries it is widely accepted that self-management tools and related costs should be completely or partly subsidized by the society. In such case, the services need to be purchased via public procurement processes.

Pre-commercial procurement refers to the situation where a public body is buying research and development work from companies. The European Union has proposed a model for applying PCP in harmony with the existing public procurement legislation (Figure 1). The model highlights the difference of “pre-commercial” and “commercial” part of the total procurement process. In the start of the pre-commercial development activity companies are selected to participate based on a public tendering process. The pre-commercial tendering process does not fall under WTO’s (World Trade Organization) Government Procurement Agreement (GPA) nor the national procurement legislation and the new EU public procurement directive (2014/24/EU). Therefore, it can be carried out along a lighter and faster process as compared with the conventional public procurement process. The pre-commercial development process involves parallel development of ideas by multiple companies. After the initial awards, the development process is carried out in three phases with evaluations at the end of each phase. During the process the number of companies reduces as only part of the companies qualify to continue to the next phase. The interactive and iterative development process of the PCP model is particularly intended to produce new innovations applicable to real-world problems. The model helps to steer the development of solutions towards the concrete needs of the procurers and end-users. IPRs (Intellectual Property Rights) are left partly or completely with the supplier companies to ensure further exploitation. Following with the risk-benefit principle, own investment to the R&D work is required from the suppliers. After the pre-commercial part the procurer shall organize a commercial tendering process in order to implement the R&D results as an operational service.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/pre-commercial-procurement>

Figure 1. Pre-commercial procurement model proposed by the European Union (EU COM 2007:799)

3. PERSONAL HEALTH SERVICE INTEROPERABILITY

The PCP model referred above is well fitted for personal health service development where there is a high potential for exploiting advanced ICT. New technology enables monitoring of health parameters with minimal user effort and with automatic feedback based on intelligent analysis of monitoring data. Advances in natural language processing (e.g. automatic language translation) provide a basis for intelligent cross-border health applications. IoT-technologies (Internet of Things) enables health related data to be effectively collected from devices and sensors. These developments hold the promise of empowering the patients for self-care and thereby reducing the demand pressure towards conventional healthcare services.

The PCP-model is expected to produce disruptive innovations as it leaves considerable freedom for the companies to develop new solutions. It is left to the companies to select which technologies they apply in the service development. However, it is the procurers' responsibility to define the interfaces for connecting the services with the rest of the service system and the clinical processes. The healthcare provider has an EHR system (Electronic Health Record) which the clinicians intensively use in the clinical process to access and enter patient data (Kalra, 2006). Additionally the health provider may maintain a PHR system (Personal Health Record) where the patient can access and enter patient data (Jones et al., 2010). Various types of applications and services are used for collecting health monitoring data and for supporting health delivery in the case of acute illness. For example, a service may help the care givers to access the essential health history of the patient as depicted in Figure 2. The service should be able to retrieve such information from the EHR or PHR system. Also in the case of supporting chronic disease management the exchange of data with electronic health records is crucial (White et al., 2016). Integration of monitoring systems with EHR and PHR systems would allow self-measurement data to be directly made available to the clinicians. Unfortunately the interface for data exchange is rarely available: many EHR and PHR systems still lack the required capabilities to connect with external services.

Figure 2. Personal health service exploits an open interface in providing access to patient's critical health history in the context of acute illness

Another challenge arises from the differences of healthcare system infrastructures between countries. Although interoperability standards exist and are adopted by many EHR systems there are national differences in the way standards are implemented. Therefore, personal health systems intended for international markets should be capable of using variable standards and clinical coding systems in order to connect with local EHR and PHR systems. This capability is especially important when the application shall support cross-border health scenarios. For example, in the case of acute illness abroad a personal application should be able to support the care process in the visited country.

4. CASE: DECIPHER PCP

The PCP process carried out in the DECIPHER² project was aimed at the development of a mobile service supporting cross-border health. The objective was to support chronic disease management and acute care episodes faced during travelling or living abroad. The PCP was a joint action of three procurers: NHS/Trustech (Manchester/UK), ESTAR (Toscana/Italy) and TicSalut (Catalonia/Spain). The process was led by AQUAS (Spain) and supported by Anci Innovazione (Italy), Eurecat (Spain) and VTT (Finland).

The process followed the model depicted in Figure 1. In the public tendering process, nine companies were selected to participate phase 1. In subsequent phases, the number of companies was reduced to six and three respectively. The development work carried out in the project was guided via the requirements and evaluation criteria set out in the challenge brief of the invitation to tender (ITT). The intention was to avoid detailed specifications, and instead formulate problems to be solved, thereby leaving room for participating companies to propose innovative solutions. Along with this freedom came the need to monitor and evaluate the outcomes of the development activity during the PCP process. In line with Figure 1, the development of technical solutions took place in three consecutive steps. During each phase the companies were requested to provide a Interim Outcome Report (IOR) which included the relevant service descriptions and demonstrations reflecting the current status of development. In the subsequent phases the companies were requested to provide service concept descriptions (phase 1), initial prototypes (phase 2) and final prototypes (phase 3). The MOR provided a way to follow the progress and give feedback to the companies before the end of the phase. The final results were evaluated after each phase by expert groups consisting of project partners and external experts. Based on the evaluation the companies granted for next phase were selected.

All resulting applications of the PCP process included basic functionalities related Diabetes management and the functionality to support quick access to essential health data in the context of urgent health episodes. Typically the applications included sections for inserting and viewing important health related parameters such as medication, physical activity, encounters, nutrition, etc. (Figure 3a). Additionally the applications included functionalities for guiding the patient for self-care and providing feedback (Figure 3b). In most applications it was possible to define a subset of data to be quickly available in the user interface in the case of emergency (Figure 3c). Also the idea of providing automatic emergency calls was presented (Figure 3d). Companies addressed the cross-border aspect by claiming support to standard interfaces for data exchange and support for language translations of static and dynamic contents.

² <http://decipherpcp.eu>

Figure 3. Examples of application screenshots by PCP supplier companies.
(a) Nextage/Camelot³, (b) GNOMON⁴, (c-d) eResult⁵.

5. ENSURING INTEROPERABILITY

The use cases targeted by DECIPHER are chronic disease management and unplanned care episodes abroad. As discussed in Section 3 such use cases evidently benefit from a connection between the personal health service and the local EHR or PHR system. Unfortunately, such connection was not possible during the project lifetime for two main reasons. PHR interfaces were included in future development plans of the procurers, but were not available for use in the project. On the other hand, access to either live PHR or copies containing real patients' data was not possible in the context of the technological research and development activity due to privacy related reasons. In addition to the DECIPHER procurers, a similar situation prevails in many other countries and districts. In such case, it is important to ensure that the solutions being developed in the PCP process are compatible with international standards and can be integrated with the EHR or PHR at a later stage.

The DECIPHER project took the approach of defining the compatibility with HL7 CCD (Continuity of Care Document) content specification as a minimum requirement (Benson, 2016; Gordon et al., 2012). This choice follows the approach adopted also for the cross-border patient summary in the epSOS⁶ project. The objective of DECIPHER was not to be dependent on epSOS infrastructure, since it is still unclear if it will be implemented and largely available. However, it was considered useful to adopt a similar CDA-based (Clinical Document Architecture) data structure to facilitate possible epSOS integration in the future. The ITT also required the solutions to be flexible, allowing additional standards to be supported as needed. For example HL7/FHIR (Benson, 2016) (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) has received wide interest and may become a dominant EHR/PHR interoperability standard in the future.

The monitoring and evaluation mechanism described in Section 4 already enabled to follow how the companies complied with the interoperability requirements. In order to support the development of standard-based applications, the project also provided a test server enabling the participant companies to store and retrieve personal health data in standard form. The DECIPHER test server (DTS) provided an open service interface towards the companies' applications thereby simulating a PHR connection. The overall architecture of the server is depicted in Figure 4.

³ <http://nextage-on.com/>, <http://www.camelotbio.com/>

⁴ www.opendecipher.gr

⁵ <http://www.eresult.it/en-us/>

⁶ www.epsos.eu

Figure 4. DECIPHER Test Server architecture

The test server maintains a collection of test user (“patient”) accounts and corresponding personal health data in the form of CCD document files. The test server includes a “test user manager”, which enables the developers of the companies to create test user accounts and corresponding security credentials. The application under development can access the test user’s health data via REST API calls (Application Programming Interface). The REST API functionality enables the application to read and write data items managed by the CCD document file. The DTS enables read and write operations focusing on particular entries or the complete record. Figure 5 illustrates the CCD file operations and the standard entry types.

Figure 5. The CCD document file simulates a personal data storage for the needs of service testing

The DTS provides only the data storage and related management functionality. It depends on the application how it displays the stored information for the user and which information is collected from the user and stored in the DTS. For testing purposes, the DTS provides a web viewer for showing users’ stored data as depicted in Figure 4.

Initially 9 companies were selected to the DECIPHER PCP process based on the tenders received in response to the ITT. The DTS was used by 7 companies. Although, the platform was available already in phase 1, it was more useful in phases 2 and 3, where actual implementations were developed. The companies participating in these phases were: Nextage/Camelot (phases 2&3), GNOMON (phases 2&3), eResult (phases 2&3), Linkcare (phase 2), Nissatech (phase 2) and alterAid (phase 2).

A questionnaire was made to the companies after phase 2. It revealed that the companies were in general happy with the DTS. They clearly expressed the wish to have access to open APIs and sandboxes enabling the exchange of data with the real PHR and EHR systems of the procurers. In the absence of such access, the DTS was considered to be a viable solution. In addition to testing the standard-based data exchange the companies expressed the need to test with other standards (especially FHIR) and with different authentication and authorization protocols, besides the basic authentication provided by the DTS.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

During the past decades considerable efforts have been focused in ensuring connectivity of clinical systems. Recently, the importance of interoperability between personal health services and clinical data storages has attracted increasing attention. As interconnected health ecosystems are emerging the needs for testing the interoperability of health applications is increasing. Major health record manufacturers are now developing new functionalities, which enable personal health services to be connected with EHR/PHR systems⁷. The ecosystems are increasingly being built based on the HL7 FHIR draft standard. FHIR is especially appreciated by developers as it employs modern web technologies and enables faster application development. FHIR defines base resources, frameworks and APIs. Thereby, it enables a “platform-based” architecture (Benson, 2016), which is particularly well-suited for supporting connected ecosystems. One example is, national PHR of Finland, which is currently being set up aside with the national “Kanta EHR archive”.

The ecosystem is currently providing an open FHIR test environment (“sandbox”) with OAuth 2.0 authorisation for supporting companies in the development of connected applications⁸. The implemented PHR exploits the open source HAPI-FHIR reference implementation⁹.

Interoperability is a major challenge especially in the context of cross-border health solutions. In the DECIPHER PCP project the standard HL7 CCD structure was adopted as a common tool to describe the health history of a patient and transfer it between systems. The CCD was selected, since in the beginning of the PCP process, FHIR was not yet available and CCD matched best with the intended functionalities of the applications.

The project provided a test server, which enabled application developers to test their solutions for PHR connectivity over a REST API. The objective of the DECIPHER test server was to provide a testing tool for the companies to be used in parallel with other testing methods. This approach was appreciated by the companies, as revealed by the feedback collected from the companies. Some of the companies participating the PCP used their own test servers or those freely available¹⁰ to test with FHIR. The DTS is planned to be exploited and further developed in the framework of follow-on research projects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The paper is based on work carried out in the DECIPHER project jointly funded by the European Commission and the project participants Anci Innovazione, AQUAS, ESTAR, Eurecat, NHS/Trustech, TicSalut and VTT.

REFERENCES

- Benson, T., 2016. *Principles of Health Interoperability*. Springer, Switzerland.
- Franz, B. et al, 2015. Applying FHIR in an Integrated Health Monitoring System. *EJBI*, Vol. 11, No. 2.
- Gordon P. et al, 2012. Processes and Outcomes of Developing a Continuity of Care Document for Use as a Personal Health Record by People Living with HIV/AIDS in New York City. *International journal of medical informatics*, Vol. 81, No. 10, e63-e73.
- Hommen, L. and Rolfstam, M., 2009. Public Procurement and Innovation – Towards a Taxonomy. *Journal of Public Procurement*, Vol. 9, No. 1, 17-56.
- Jones, D. A. et al, 2010. Characteristics of personal health records: Findings of the medical library Association/National library of medicine joint electronic personal health record task force. *Journal of the Medical Library Association: JMLA*, Vol. 98, No. 3, 243–249.

⁷ <https://open.epic.com/>

⁸ <http://fhirsandbox.kanta.fi/kanta-phr-sandbox-ui/>

⁹ <http://hapifhir.io/>

¹⁰ <http://fhirtest.uhn.ca/>

- Kalra, D., 2006. Electronic health record standards. *IMIA Yearbook 2006: Assessing Information – Technologies for Health*, Vol. 1, No. 1, 136–144.
- Klersy C et al, 2009. A meta-analysis of remote monitoring of heart failure patients. *J Am Coll Cardiol*, Vol. 54, No. 18, 1683-1694.
- Li, Y. C. et al. (2012). A global travelers' electronic health record template standard for personal health records. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association: JAMIA*, Vol. 19, No. 1, 134–136.
- Orsama, A. L., et al, 2013. Active assistance technology reduces glycosylated hemoglobin and weight in individuals with type 2 diabetes: Results of a theory-based randomized trial. *Diabetes Technology & Therapeutics*, Vol. 15, No. 8, 662–669.
- White, H. et al., 2016. Requirements and access needs of patients with chronic disease to their hospital electronic health record: results of a cross-sectional questionnaire survey. *BMJ Open*, Vol. 6, No. 10.